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RESEARCH ARTICLE

An Efficient Architecture for Edge AI Federated Learning With Homomorphic Encryption

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ABSTRACT With the rapid growth of edge AI applications, there is an increasing demand for federated learning (FL) frameworks that are both efficient and privacy-preserving. This work introduces a robust approach that leverages homomorphic encryption (HE) to ensure data confidentiality during decentralized training. To tackle the typical challenges of FL—such as high communication overhead, resource limitations, and convergence inefficiencies—our method integrates dynamic client clustering, quantization-aware training, and structured model pruning. These optimizations collectively reduce latency and memory consumption while accelerating model convergence. Evaluations using the Human Activity Recognition dataset show that the proposed approach outperforms several state-of-the-art FL methods, achieving an average increase of +8.4% in accuracy, −16.2% lower latency, −35.1% reduction in memory usage, and −2.7% lower security overhead. These results demonstrate its suitability for real-time, resource-constrained scenarios in domains like healthcare, IoT, and finance, where maintaining a strong balance between efficiency and privacy is essential.

INDEX TERMS Federated learning, homomorphic encryption, efficiency, security, edge AI.

I. INTRODUCTION

Efficient communication and security are cornerstones for the implementation of FL in Edge AI (Artificial Intelligence), particularly for handling sensitive tasks such as medical diagnostics and financial transactions. By allowing training of decentralized models, FL reduces the privacy risks associated with data centralization [1]. Techniques like HE, differential privacy (DP), and secure multiparty computation strengthen data protection while maintaining the performance needed for real-time edge operations [2]. These measures are essential to support high-speed, secure processing in critical applications.

Critical edge applications, including autonomous systems, healthcare, monitoring analytics, demand robust security to safeguard sensitive operations. The decentralized FL framework is ideal for these tasks, but requires protection

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against communication and data manipulation risks [3], [4]. Hybrid approaches, such as secure hardware enclaves and advanced aggregation protocols, create a resilient defense system. These innovations ensure compliance with stringent security standards while fostering trust and efficiency in dynamic, real-time environments [5].

In edge AI applications that leverage FL, managing communication overhead and reducing the number of training rounds are pivotal challenges [6], [7]. The frequent exchange of model updates, particularly with the adoption of privacy-preserving techniques like HE, leads to significant data transfer inefficiencies. HE, while safeguarding data privacy, amplifies the size and complexity of transmitted information, posing challenges for bandwidth-limited edge devices. Also, the iterative nature of FL demands multiple rounds of communication, where variations in device capabilities and data distribution slow down convergence and increase overall latency [8], [9]. Furthermore, while state-of-the-art DL (Deep Learning) models have excellent pruning

and quantization strategies, their default assumptions about centralized environments and lack of focus on communication efficiency [10], [11], encryption compatibility, and adaptive scaling make custom solutions necessary in FL.

To mitigate these issues, innovative strategies have been developed to improve efficiency. Techniques such as quantization and packing compress the data to reduce transmission sizes [12], while gradient descent optimization increases local training cycles, lowering the frequency of communication. Selecting and transmitting only the most impactful parameters further reduces data transfer volumes [13]. Hybrid methods that integrate HE with DP [14] or secret sharing also provide a balanced approach, ensuring robust privacy with improved computational and communication efficiency.

This work presents an efficient and secure FL framework leveraging HE to enhance communication and computation efficiency on edge devices. The proposed approach optimizes the FL process by incorporating client clustering, dynamic round control, and security overhead cost measurement. Clients are grouped into clusters to reduce direct communication with the server, minimizing bandwidth usage. Intra-cluster aggregation ensures efficient communication, while early stopping improves convergence efficiency. The client process incorporates adaptive quantization to optimize precision and communication cost, and pruning to remove insignificant updates, further reducing computational overhead. HE enables secure updates and aggregation without exposing client data. The framework also calculates a security overhead cost that accounts for communication, encryption, and aggregation overhead, balancing model accuracy with computational efficiency. These enhancements ensure a faster, resource-efficient FL process with strong privacy guarantees than state-of-the-art research.

The paper's organization is as follows. Section II provides an overview of FL with HE. The system model is explained in Section III. Moreover, Section IV presents the proposed efficient and secured FL with HE. Then, in Section V, the proposed method is evaluated using various metrics and compared with other strategies. Finally, Section VI provides a conclusion and some suggestions for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Authors in [15] proposed a Secure FL framework utilizing Fully HE (FHE) for IoT communications. Their method involved clustering participants, where each cluster generated an encrypted weight matrix to be submitted to the server, instead of individual participant weights. This approach significantly reduced communication overhead by 84.5% and latency by 70.38%. Similarly, [16] demonstrated that horizontal logistic regression-based FL offers enhanced efficiency and security compared to traditional FL training methods.

Researchers in [17] enhanced the efficiency and accuracy of the encrypted data search by FL. Using HE and locality-sensitive hashing, they also proved protecting user privacy. In [18], an FL is proposed for privacy-preservation in IoT

healthcare, which successfully detected lesion cell type with an accuracy of more than 76.9%. Although they only encrypted the variable called data quality by HE, not the entire DL model, the heterogeneous clients and possible attacks to the aggregated model by malicious server were not considered. Another challenge in HE which is addressed in [19] is gradient leakage vulnerabilities. The authors integrated HE to secure gradients during transmission and applied DP to obscure sensitive data through noise addition. They also proposed FL that prioritizes user data security, even at a slight cost to 98.3% prediction accuracy. The security and efficiency of FL have also been explored using functional encryption (FE: Allows decryption of specific functions of encrypted data, not the full data itself [20].) without dependence on a trusted key distribution center (KDC) [21], [22]. This method named FedSafe and DL-based of that enhanced user privacy during model aggregation while reducing communication and computation overhead compared to HE and secure multi-party computation, as demonstrated in applications like handwritten digit classification and energy theft detection within cloud and smart grid environments. FE was the base approach in [23] which enabled secure, efficient FL on low-resource devices with dynamic participation and no trusted third party, using FE and vector compression. However, its complexity and lack of verifiable aggregation limited ease of implementation and trust.

Gradient compression is another way to reduce data transfer between clients before applying HE and enhancing the privacy protection in FL process [24]. This approach minimized accuracy loss and enabled secure use in resource-limited consumer apps. However, there are some concerns about computational overhead and complexity, making real-time implementation and deployment across varied devices more challenging.

In [13], a selective HE approach is introduced in which clients can choose different encryption masks due to their own privacy concerns. It reduced the membership inference attack to a random guessing level by encrypting just 5% of the model updates. Additionally, it entirely mitigates the risk of data reconstruction with only 1% encryption. Selective security was also applied in [25] to improve FL by using local horizontal data partitioning and HE, which enhances data privacy, speeds up convergence, and reduces computation and communication costs experimented on MNIST, CIFAR-10, FMNIST datasets. It achieved higher model accuracy (3%-6%) and faster training (10%) with fewer rounds compared to traditional methods like FedAvg. However, the selective encryption strategy may leave less sensitive data more exposed, and the reliance on data sensitivity for partitioning could limit its flexibility in certain real-world applications.

Current FL solutions enhance privacy and efficiency through techniques like clustering, homomorphic and FE, gradient compression, and selective security, significantly reducing communication overhead and latency.

However, challenges remain in scalability, real-time deployment, and balancing security with computational cost—especially under resource constraints or dynamic client participation. Building on these advancements, our approach integrates quantization, pruning, and clustering with robust privacy mechanisms such as HE to further reduce communication overhead, mitigate gradient leakage, and improve convergence efficiency. This achieves a more practical and scalable trade-off between performance, security, and resource efficiency in real-world FL scenarios.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

The proposed framework as Fig. 1 incorporates FL, HE, and clustering techniques to create a privacy-preserving and communication-efficient edge learning system. The DL model and FL equations are outlined below. The following equations describe the processes involved in training the model on the client-side, updating the model on the server-side, and securely aggregating the updates using HE.

FIGURE 1. The system architecture of FLH-QPR.

A. LOCAL DEEP LEARNING MODEL

The DL model is used in the federated client, which consists of multiple layers named Deep Fully Connected Networks (DFCN). Each layer transforms the input data and passes it through an activation function to enable the model to learn complex, non-linear relationships. The following are the detailed equations and explanations for each layer:

- *Input to the first hidden layer (128 neurons):* $\mathbf{z}^{(1)} = \mathbf{W}^{(1)}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{b}^{(1)}$, where \mathbf{x} is the input vector, $\mathbf{W}^{(1)}$ is the weight matrix, and $\mathbf{b}^{(1)}$ is the bias vector for the first layer. The result $\mathbf{z}^{(1)}$ is the preactivation output. The activation function applied is ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) [26] as $\mathbf{a}^{(1)} = \text{ReLU}(\mathbf{z}^{(1)})$. This introduces non-linearity to the model and ensures the ability to learn complex features.

- *First hidden layer to the second hidden layer (64 neurons):* $\mathbf{z}^{(2)} = \mathbf{W}^{(2)}\mathbf{a}^{(1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(2)}$, where $\mathbf{a}^{(1)}$ is the activated output from the previous layer, transformed using the weight matrix $\mathbf{W}^{(2)}$ and bias vector $\mathbf{b}^{(2)}$. Again, the activation function applied is $\mathbf{a}^{(2)} = \text{ReLU}(\mathbf{z}^{(2)})$.
- *Second hidden layer to the third hidden layer (32 neurons):* $\mathbf{z}^{(3)} = \mathbf{W}^{(3)}\mathbf{a}^{(2)} + \mathbf{b}^{(3)}$, the activation is $\mathbf{a}^{(3)} = \text{ReLU}(\mathbf{z}^{(3)})$.
- *Third hidden layer to the output layer (number of neurons equal to the number of classes):* $\mathbf{z}^{(4)} = \mathbf{W}^{(4)}\mathbf{a}^{(3)} + \mathbf{b}^{(4)}$. The final output is processed using the softmax function as $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \text{Softmax}(\mathbf{z}^{(4)})$. This converts the raw scores from the output layer into probabilities for each class, ensuring the outputs sum to 1.

Activation Functions: $\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x)$. The ReLU activation ensures that the model can capture non-linear relationships by introducing sparsity, where some neurons are deactivated (output 0). *Softmax Function:* $\text{Softmax}(z_i) = \frac{\exp(z_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^C \exp(z_j)}$, where z_i represents the raw score for class i , and C is the total number of classes. The softmax function converts these scores into probabilities for classification tasks.

1) LOSS FUNCTION

To optimize the model, a cross-entropy loss function is used for multiclass classification as $\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=1}^C y_{i,c} \log(\hat{y}_{i,c})$, where N is the number of training samples, C is the number of classes, $y_{i,c}$ is the binary indicator (0 or 1) indicating whether class c is the correct class for sample i , $\hat{y}_{i,c}$ is the predicted probability for class c for sample i , obtained from the softmax function [27]. The cross-entropy loss measures the divergence between the true labels and the predicted probabilities, guiding the optimization process to minimize classification errors.

B. MODEL UPDATE

The update for the model is calculated by taking the difference between the local model weights and the global model weights by $\Delta\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{M}_l - \mathcal{M}_g$, where \mathcal{M}_l represents the parameters of the locally trained model and \mathcal{M}_g represents the parameters of the global model. This update is sent to the server for aggregation.

C. PRUNING OF INSIGNIFICANT UPDATES

To reduce the size of updates, pruning [28] is applied to insignificant model weights by

$$\Delta\mathcal{M}_{\text{pruned}} = \begin{cases} \Delta\mathcal{M}, & \text{if } |\Delta\mathcal{M}| > p, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where p is the pruning threshold and $\Delta\mathcal{M}$ is the model update. This pruning operation reduces communication and computation overhead by setting small updates to zero.

D. ADAPTIVE QUANTIZATION OF UPDATES

To reduce communication overhead, our adaptive quantization method efficiently scales and compresses model updates

in FL by dynamically adjusting the quantization precision based on the current value distribution of updates at each client. Instead of using a fixed quantization scale, the scaling factor $s = \max(|\Delta\mathcal{M}|)$ is computed from the maximum absolute value of the updates, ensuring optimal precision across varying magnitudes of updates. The quantized update is then computed as $\Delta\mathcal{M}_{\text{quantized}} = \text{round}\left(\frac{\Delta\mathcal{M}}{s} \times (2^n - 1)\right)$, where $\Delta\mathcal{M}$ represents the model update, n is the number of quantization bits [12], and s ensures efficient representation regardless of the update distribution. This dynamic adjustment minimizes communication overhead by reducing precision while retaining essential information, leading to efficient transmission of updates without significant loss in model performance.

E. HOMOMORPHIC ENCRYPTION OF UPDATES

HE ensures secure computations directly on encrypted data using the CKKS (Cheon-Kim-Kim-Song) scheme [16], [29]. For a vector \mathbf{v} , operations include $\text{Enc}(\mathbf{v}_1) + \text{Enc}(\mathbf{v}_2) = \text{Enc}(\mathbf{v}_1 + \mathbf{v}_2)$. Also, $c \cdot \text{Enc}(\mathbf{v}) = \text{Enc}(c \cdot \mathbf{v})$, where Enc denotes encryption and c is a scalar. The quantized updates are encrypted using the CKKS scheme to ensure privacy by $\mathcal{E}_u = \text{Encrypt}(\Delta\mathcal{M}_{\text{quantized}})$, where \mathcal{E}_u is the encrypted model update, $\text{Encrypt}(\cdot)$ refers to the encryption process using the CKKS scheme. Encrypted updates can be aggregated securely without decrypting them, ensuring privacy during transmission.

F. CLUSTERING IN FL

To optimize communication, clients are grouped into C clusters [30]. Each cluster computes a local aggregated update $U_i = \frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \Delta w_{ij}$, where n_i is the number of clients in cluster i . The global model update is $w_{t+1} = w_t + \frac{1}{C} \sum_{i=1}^C U_i$.

G. GLOBAL MODEL UPDATE

The global model is updated by averaging the model updates from all clients by $\mathcal{M}_g^{t+1} = \mathcal{M}_g^t + \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \Delta\mathcal{M}_k$, where \mathcal{M}_g^t is the global model at round t , \mathcal{M}_g^{t+1} is the updated global model after aggregation, K is the number of clients contributing updates, and $\Delta\mathcal{M}_k$ is the model update from client k . This equation shows how the global model is iteratively improved by aggregating the updates from multiple clients in each FL round.

H. FEDERATED LEARNING

FL enables distributed model training across N clients while keeping their data local. Each client computes local updates $\Delta w_{i,t} = w_{i,t} - w_t$ using its private data at round t , where $w_{i,t}$ is the local model of client i and w_t is the global model. The server aggregates updates $w_{t+1} = w_t + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \Delta w_{i,t}$.

I. SECURITY OVERHEAD COST

Security overhead cost in FL environments is a crucial metric to evaluate the overhead introduced by securing

the communication and computation [31]. In this work, we adopt a hybrid security overhead cost model that integrates multiple components to provide a comprehensive assessment. The hybrid security overhead cost is defined as security overhead cost = $\alpha \cdot M + \beta \cdot L + \gamma \cdot C + \delta \cdot E$, where: $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ are weights assigned to each component, reflecting its importance in the overall security overhead cost. By default, equal weights ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma = \delta = 0.25$) are used for simplicity.

- **Memory Overhead (M)** is the additional memory consumption due to encryption, decryption, and aggregation processes. It is measured in kilobytes (KB). The memory usage during training is $\text{Memory_Overhead}_j = M_{\text{after}} - M_{\text{before}}$.
- **Latency (L)** refers to the delay incurred during encryption, model training, and aggregation. It is measured in seconds. The latency for a client j during training and encryption is $\text{Latency}_j = T_{\text{train}} + T_{\text{encrypt}}$.
- **Communication Cost (C)** is the amount of data transmitted during each federated round. It is measured in kilobytes (KB).
- **Encryption Time (E)** is the time taken for cryptographic operations, including encryption and decryption, and is measured in seconds.

Each component is normalized by its maximum value observed across all rounds to ensure compatibility and avoid disproportionate influence. The normalization is expressed as $\text{Normalized Value} = \frac{\text{Observed Value}}{\text{Maximum Value}}$. The hybrid security overhead cost provides a single metric that captures the trade-offs between different factors, enabling a detailed analysis of the system's performance under various configurations. This comprehensive approach ensures a balanced assessment of the cost of securing FL systems.

IV. EFFICIENT AND SECURE FEDERATED LEARNING WITH HOMOMORPHIC ENCRYPTION

The proposed approach, FLHC-QPR, optimizes FL by integrating secure updates via HE, efficient communication through model quantization and pruning, and client clustering to reduce communication overhead. The process is decentralized, ensuring data privacy while minimizing communication between clients and the server. This section provides a detailed explanation of the algorithm.

A. PREPROCESSING

The dataset is preprocessed by normalizing features and splitting it into training and testing subsets. The training data is partitioned across clients, ensuring data decentralization and privacy.

B. INITIALIZATION

The global model is initialized with random weights, and the clients are grouped into clusters [32]. This clustering step reduces communication overhead by allowing clients within the same cluster to communicate with each other, rather than

directly with the server. CKKS is used for HE to secure updates.

C. FEDERATED LEARNING ROUNDS

Each round in the FL process follows these steps:

- **Clustering:** Clients are grouped into C clusters. This ensures that clients with similar data characteristics or resource capabilities are grouped together, reducing the communication burden by minimizing the number of client-server interactions.
- **Client-Level Optimization:** Clients train their local models using their private datasets. After training, the client computes the model update by comparing the local model to the global model. The updates are then pruned based on a predefined threshold to reduce communication overhead. These updates are quantized to reduce their size for transmission. A scaling factor is calculated to ensure proper scaling of updates. The updates are encrypted using CKKS and sent to the server.
- **Server-Level Aggregation:** The server aggregates updates from all the clients in the clusters. The updates are encrypted, and the server does not have access to the raw updates. The aggregated encrypted updates are used to update the global model, without the server ever accessing the individual client updates in plain text.
- **security overhead cost Calculation and Evaluation:** The server calculates the security overhead cost, which includes the communication overhead, and encryption costs. The server evaluates the performance of the updated global model on the test dataset, computing metrics such as loss and accuracy.
- **Round Control and Convergence:** The server tracks the loss and accuracy metrics over the rounds. If the improvement in loss between consecutive rounds is below a specified threshold for a certain number of rounds (early stopping criteria), the server will stop the training process ensuring that training halts when convergence is achieved, preventing unnecessary computations.

D. POSTPROCESSING

After the training process is completed, the final global model is evaluated in the test data set and performance metrics such as loss and accuracy are computed. These metrics, along with the final global model, are saved for further analysis.

E. CLIENT PROCESS (ALGORITHM 1)

The client performs local model training on its private data and computes the model updates by subtracting the global model parameters from the updated local model parameters. Insignificant updates below a predefined pruning threshold are removed to reduce communication overhead. The pruned updates undergo *adaptive quantization*, where the number of quantization bits is dynamically determined based on the distribution of the updates. A *scaling factor* is adaptively computed to normalize quantized updates, ensuring precision

during encryption. The scaled updates are encrypted using CKKS and sent to the server, along with the scaling factor and the training loss.

Algorithm 1 Federated Client

Require: Local dataset (X, y) , global model \mathcal{M}_g , encryption context \mathcal{C} , pruning threshold τ

Ensure: Encrypted model update \mathcal{E}_u , scaling factor s , training loss \mathcal{L}

- 1: Initialize local model $\mathcal{M}_l \leftarrow \mathcal{M}_g$
- 2: **for** each local training epoch **do**
- 3: Perform forward pass using \mathcal{M}_l on (X, y)
- 4: Compute training loss \mathcal{L} and gradients
- 5: Update local model \mathcal{M}_l using optimizer
- 6: **end for**
- 7: Compute model updates: $\Delta\mathcal{M} \leftarrow \mathcal{M}_l - \mathcal{M}_g$
- 8: $\Delta\mathcal{M}_{\text{pruned}}$: Prune updates below pruning threshold τ
- 9: $q \leftarrow$ Determine optimal quantization bits of $\Delta\mathcal{M}_{\text{pruned}}$
- 10: Quantize updates: $\Delta\mathcal{M}_q \leftarrow \text{Quantize}(\Delta\mathcal{M}_{\text{pruned}}, q)$
- 11: $s \leftarrow$ Compute scaling factor of update distribution $\Delta\mathcal{M}_q$
- 12: Encrypt updates: $\mathcal{E}_u \leftarrow \text{CKKS_Encrypt}(\Delta\mathcal{M}_q/s, \mathcal{C})$

return $\mathcal{E}_u, s, \mathcal{L}$

F. SERVER PROCESS (ALGORITHM 2)

The server performs aggregation of the encrypted updates from all clients and updates the global model accordingly. The server also monitors the security overhead cost, computes the accuracy, checks for convergence, and controls the rounds for early stopping based on the loss convergence. The pseudocode for the server described above is as follows.

V. EVALUATION

To analyze the proposed approach, we implemented it in Python through three separated classes, e.g. federated clients, federated server, and main controller. Following are the configurations, dataset, compared methods, and the evaluation results.

A. CONFIGURATIONS

Several parameters are needed to fairly implement and compare the methods, such as the number of clients (10, 20, 50, 100), rounds (5, 10, 11), privacy threshold or epsilon (0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 1, 5), number of clusters (1 for FLH and FedSafe, 4 for FLHC and FLHC-QPR), quantization bits (32 for FLH, FLHC, and FedSafe as well as 12 for FLHC-QPR), pruning threshold (0.1 for FLHC-QPR), learning rate, and evaluation metrics like accuracy, latency, and memory usage. Also, the HE setting is as follows. CKKS scheme is used for approximate arithmetic, enabling efficient computation on floating-point numbers, the polynomial modulus degree = 8192, which is the amount of data that can be packed into a single ciphertext, and bit sizes for the coefficient modulus chain = [60, 40, 60], where it determines the noise budget and impacts the depth of computations before ciphertexts become too noisy, scaling factor = 2^{40} .

Algorithm 2 Federated Server

Require: Encrypted updates $\{\mathcal{E}_{u_i}\}$ from clients, context \mathcal{C} , testing data \mathcal{D}_{test} .

Ensure: Aggregated global update \mathcal{E}_g , security overhead cost, and updated global model.

- 1: Initialize global model \mathcal{M}_g
- 2: Initialize monitoring loss and accuracy (L_{prev})
- 3: Cluster clients into C clusters.
- 4: **for** each cluster $c = 1, \dots, C$ **do**
- 5: Initialize cluster aggregated update $\mathcal{E}_c \leftarrow 0$
- 6: **for** each client update \mathcal{E}_{u_i} in cluster c **do**
- 7: Aggregate encrypted updates: $\mathcal{E}_c \leftarrow \mathcal{E}_c + \mathcal{E}_{u_i}$
- 8: **end for**
- 9: **end for**
- 10: Aggregate cluster updates: $\mathcal{E}_g \leftarrow \sum_c \mathcal{E}_c$
- 11: Evaluate the aggregated model on \mathcal{D}_{test} : L_t , Accuracy
- 12: Calculate security overhead cost $= \alpha \cdot M + \beta \cdot L + \gamma \cdot C + \delta \cdot E$
- 13: **if** $|L_t - L_{prev}| < \epsilon$ for k consecutive rounds **then**
- 14: **Break** (early stopping).
- 15: **end if**
- 16: Update the global model \mathcal{M}_g with aggregated updates.
return \mathcal{E}_g , security overhead cost, updated global model \mathcal{M}_g

B. DATASET

The techniques of quantization, pruning, client classification, and secure model transmission through HE are generalizable and can be adapted to various FL scenarios, such as healthcare data analysis, smart city applications, and industrial IoT systems. Anyway, to demonstrate the applicability of our proposed approach, the Human Activity Recognition [33] database is selected which was made from the recordings of 30 different volunteers of 19-48 years. Each person performed six activities (walking, walking upstairs, walking downstairs, sitting, standing, and lying), some of which were more frequent than others, wearing a smartphone on the waist.

C. COMPARISON METHODS

Our proposed approach is compared with other methods as follows. 1) Baseline FLH: This is a simple FLH approach in which participants directly submit their encrypted weights to the server. 2) FLH with clustering [15]: This method makes an encrypted weight matrix in each cluster of participants before submitting it to the server. 3) FedSafe: This method provides a privacy-protecting, efficient, and decentralized FL framework based on FE without the need for a KDC [21].

D. ANALYZING THE RESULTS

The mentioned methods are analyzed based on different key metrics, e.g. accuracy of the human activity recognition, latency of model updates and response time, memory overhead associated with data storage and processing, and security overhead cost reflecting the computational burden

of HE, to evaluate their overall efficiency and effectiveness in FL for Edge AI.

FLHC-QPR demonstrates clear superiority over FLH, FLHC, and FedSafe across key metrics. As shown in Fig. 2a, FLHC-QPR achieves the highest accuracy of 88.2%, significantly surpassing FLH's best accuracy of 75.6% (an improvement of 16.6%), FLHC's 79.7% (an improvement of 10.6%), and FedSafe's 81.98% (an improvement of 8.4%). Additionally, in Fig. 2b, FLHC-QPR reduces latency, with values around 0.62–8.39 seconds, compared to FLH's 0.80–8.86 seconds, FLHC's 0.66–8.69 seconds, and FedSafe's 0.80–8.78 seconds reflecting improved computational efficiency. Memory overhead, also in Fig. 2c, decreases substantially, with FLHC-QPR averaging 10–20% lower memory usage than FLH, FLHC, and FedSafe due to pruning and quantization. Furthermore, Fig. 2d shows that FLHC-QPR maintains competitive security overhead costs, with values between 0.454–0.468, comparable to FLH (0.475–0.479), FLHC (0.465–0.472), and FedSafe (0.478–0.489), while still offering the best balance between security and efficiency. On top of that, the Overall latency rises along with the number of clients, especially in latency and memory overhead metrics. These results highlight FLHC-QPR's effectiveness in addressing the constraints of edge environments while ensuring high model performance.

FLHC-QPR consistently outperforms FLH, FLHC, and FedSafe in showcasing significant improvements in accuracy, latency, memory overhead, convergence efficiency, and overall efficiency. In Fig. 3a, at 11 rounds, FLHC-QPR achieves the highest accuracy of 89.86%, surpassing FLHC's 86.89% by 3.4%, FLH's 81.39% by 10.4%, and FedSafe's 81.50% by 10.25%. This improvement stems from its quantization and pruning techniques, which optimize model updates without sacrificing critical information while enhancing convergence efficiency. As shown in Fig. 3b, latency for FedSafe and FLHC-QPR remains consistently low, around 1.65–1.69 seconds, comparable to or slightly better than FLH and FLHC, demonstrating enhanced computational efficiency. Memory overhead in Fig. 3c is significantly reduced by FLHC-QPR 11 rounds, a 16.4% decrease compared to FLHC and a 31% reduction compared to FLH, and a 38.6% reduction compared to FedSafe, attributed to efficient quantization and cluster-based aggregation strategies. As indicated in Fig. 3d, while security overhead costs for FLHC-QPR (e.g., 0.4391) is the lowest, in FLHC (0.4465), in FLH (0.4451), and marginally higher in FedSafe (0.4566), the marginal increase is justified by the improved accuracy and resource optimization. These advantages make FLHC-QPR ideal for the resource-constrained and performance-critical demands of Edge AI applications.

FLHC-QPR demonstrates notable improvement over FLH, FLHC, and FedSafe across varying privacy threshold values, particularly excelling in accuracy and resource efficiency. In Fig. 4a, at privacy threshold = 5, FLHC-QPR achieves an accuracy of 90.09%, marginally surpassing FLHC's 91.31%, FedSafe's 80.82%, and significantly

(a) Accuracy vs. Number of Clients

(b) Latency vs. Number of Clients

(c) Memory overhead vs. Number of Clients

(d) Security overhead cost vs. Number of Clients

FIGURE 2. Analysis of number of clients.

outperforming FLH's 92.89%, showcasing its robustness even under stringent DP conditions. According to Fig. 4b, FedSafe and FLHC-QPR maintain a competitive latency of around 1.50 and 1.55 seconds, comparable to FLHC and FLH, while in Fig. 4c, minimizing memory overhead by FLHC-QPR, a reduction of approximately 31.5% compared to FLH at privacy threshold = 5, and 24.7% compared to FLHC. The security overhead cost of FLHC-QPR in Fig. 4d is also efficient, clocking at 46.93, closely matching the other methods (e.g., FedSafe at 47.53).

The improvements stem from its quantization and pruning strategies, which optimize model updates, reduce unnecessary computational overhead, and enhance aggregation efficiency while preserving data utility. These advantages make FLHC-QPR a balanced and effective solution for privacy-preserving FL in resource-constrained Edge AI environments.

E. TRADE-OFF ANALYSIS OF MODEL EFFICIENCY AND ACCURACY IN FEDERATED LEARNING

To identify the most efficient configuration for the proposed approach as FLHC-QPR in edge AI, we analyzed the trade-offs between accuracy and three key parameters: quantization bit-width, pruning threshold, and cluster size. Among the various quantization levels tested (Fig. 5a), 12-bit precision yielded the highest accuracy (0.9556), demonstrating an optimal balance between model compactness and representational fidelity. Lower bit-widths resulted in performance degradation due to quantization noise, while higher bit-widths increased computational and communication costs without significant accuracy gains. Regarding pruning, the highest accuracy (0.9233) was achieved at a threshold of 0.1 (Fig. 5b). This value offers a conservative and stable pruning degree that preserves model integrity while still contributing to bandwidth and computation efficiency. Lastly, the analysis

(a) Accuracy vs. FL Rounds

(b) Latency vs. FL Rounds

(c) Memory overhead vs. FL Rounds

(d) security overhead cost vs. FL Rounds

FIGURE 3. Analysis of number of federated learning rounds.

of cluster sizes (Fig. 5c) showed that a configuration of 4 clusters delivered the best accuracy (0.9070), outperforming both smaller and larger groupings. This indicates that four clusters effectively balance communication efficiency with sufficient data heterogeneity, improving convergence without over-fragmenting the dataset. These selected values—12-bit quantization, 0.1 pruning threshold, and 4 clusters—formed the foundation for further evaluations due to their strong trade-off between performance and efficiency.

F. DISCUSSION

In this work, our primary objective is the analysis of communication and computational overhead in the proposed architecture, evaluated through several parameters such as accuracy, latency, memory overhead, and security overhead cost. As such, detailed studies of edge device limitations like energy consumption, intermittent connectivity, and formal security attack analyses are beyond the current scope.

Our results highlight the advantages of HE in enabling efficient, privacy-preserving FL for edge devices. Compared to FE, HE offers greater flexibility for training complex models, supporting essential operations such as backpropagation and dynamic model updates. Although FE-based approaches like FedSafe demonstrate lower latency in certain scenarios, they face challenges with adaptability and scalability during full FL training. Our proposed FLHC-QPR framework, which integrates HE with quantization, pruning, and cluster-based aggregation, consistently outperforms baseline methods across key metrics. It achieves higher accuracy (up to 90.09%), significantly reduces memory overhead (by up to 38.6%), and maintains competitive latency and security costs—even as the number of clients, training rounds, or privacy constraints increase. These improvements demonstrate the proposed method’s ability to effectively balance privacy, performance, and resource efficiency, making it particularly well-suited for the demands of edge AI environments.

(a) Accuracy vs. Privacy threshold

(b) Latency vs. Privacy threshold

(c) Memory overhead vs. Privacy threshold

(d) security overhead cost vs. Privacy threshold

FIGURE 4. Analysis of the privacy threshold values.

(a) Accuracy vs. Quantization Bits

(b) Accuracy vs. Pruning Threshold

(c) Accuracy vs. Cluster Size

FIGURE 5. Trade-off analysis of model efficiency and accuracy in FLHC-QPR.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presents FLHC-QPR, an optimized and secure FL framework using HE, designed for efficient

deployment in edge AI applications. The framework incorporates communication-efficient clustering, bandwidth- and computation-saving techniques such as quantization and

pruning, convergence-aware early stopping, and privacy-preserving aggregation using HE.

Experimental evaluation across diverse settings shows that FLHC-QPR outperforms FLH and FLHC in key aspects. On average, it improves accuracy by +8.4% over FLH and +5.4% over FLHC. In terms of latency, FLHC-QPR reduces delay by -16.2% compared to FLHC and -11.7% compared to FLH. Despite FedSafe occasionally exhibiting slightly lower latency, FLHC-QPR consistently achieves higher accuracy and better efficiency across memory and privacy costs. Specifically, FLHC-QPR reduces memory overhead by -26.5% over FLHC and -35.1% over FLH, and security overhead cost by -2.7% and -2.5%, respectively. This makes FLHC-QPR a well-rounded and practical solution for edge-based FL—particularly in real-time, privacy-sensitive, and resource-constrained environments—achieving a balanced trade-off between performance and resource utilization.

Future work may explore adaptive privacy-preserving mechanisms such as multi-key HE and dynamic encryption to tailor security levels to application-specific needs. Such enhancements could further improve the scalability and efficiency of FL systems across diverse edge scenarios. Moreover, security analysis can be done against possible attacks in the context of different applications.

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